

Finite element study of thermal behaviour in ultra-low nickel Cr-Mn ASS welded with SMAW & GMAW techniques

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Abstract

Cr-Mn Austenitic Stainless Steel (ASS) are utilized in nuclear reprocessing plants, fast-breeder reactors, pressurised water reactors and boiling water reactors because of their ease of fabrication and welding. In this study two fillers were used, ER308L and ER308L-16, to weld ultra-low nickel Cr-Mn ASS using gas metal arc welding (GMAW) and shielded metal arc welding (SMAW) process. The simulation of the welding processes was carried out for the evaluation of stresses induced in the welding. The heat input is employed at the weld bead for modelling and analysis. From analysis, it was found that the weld bead width is less in GMAW as compared to SMAW. The transient thermal and structural analysis was carried out for evaluation of stresses in the weld using ANSYS. The weld for both welding methods was analysed using varying welding speeds. It was revealed that as the welding speed increases there is a decrease in Von-Mises stresses in the weld.

Keywords

Cr-Mn ASS, welding speed, shielded metal arc welding process, gas metal arc welding process and Von-mises stresses

Introduction

Out of all the austenitic stainless-steel grades, including the 300 series and 200 series, the Ultra-Low Nickel Cr-Mn Austenitic Stainless Steel (ULNASS) has the lowest nickel content (Ambade et al. 2024). Ultra-low Nickel Cr-Mn Austenitic Stainless Steel is becoming more popular as a substitute for traditional Cr-Ni Austenitic Stainless Steel (Naseem et al. 2024). The different types of failure analysis have shown that the failure occurs in the heat affected zone (HAZ). Therefore, the analysis of stresses developed in this region is an important factor to carry out

failure analysis in this region (Gonzalez-Velazquez 2018). The stresses developed in this region is affected by the various welding parameters which are considered during welding (Gkatzogiannis et al. 2017). This welding parameters plays a vital role in making the changes in thermal and structural stresses in the weld (Arora et al. 2019). This type of welding method used, current, voltage, and welding speed which are crucial welding characteristics (Singh and Singh 2020). The mechanical characteristics and microstructure of the weld and HAZ are significantly impacted by the heat input factor, which also directly influences the distribution of stress in the weld (Rizvi and

Ahamad 2018). The stresses developed in the weld are difficult to measure as there are changes in the chemical composition of the parent and filler materials. There are various ways for measurement of stresses in weld region. The different methods used such as analytical, numerical, destructive (drilling hole) and non-destructive (Ultrasonic, X-rays, etc). The analytical and numerical techniques are widely used for calculating the stresses developed in the weld. Recent advancements in software that can model the weld zone and compute the stresses created in the weld using finite element methods were discussed by various researchers. Using ER308L and ER308L-16 filler materials, Akbari and Sattari-far 2017 employed finite element techniques to analyse the residual stresses that developed in the heat affected zone of the two dissimilar pipes made of A106-B carbon steel and A240-TP304 stainless steel. They discovered that the two parent metals yield stresses were less than the residual stresses that developed in the joint. The residual stresses on the stainless-steel side are greater than those in the carbon steel side as the heat input diminishes. Almeida et al. 2017 simulated AISI 316L austenitic stainless steel of a tungsten inert gas butt-welding (TIG) process and compared experimental residual stresses with simulated residual stresses obtained with finite element analysis. They found that there is a 19% and 9% deviation in maximum principal stress and minimum principal stress for simulated weld bead as compared to the experimental hole-drilling method. Efa 2024 used laser beam welding for AZ31B and AA6061 for finite element simulations and found out the residual stress and maximum temperature in Laser Beam Welding (LBW). The authors found average laser beam power- 4011 Watts, velocity- 30 mm/s, spot size- 0.8 mm, and segment number-12 and predicted optimal temperature range between 1148.2 and 1158.0°C and the optimal residual stress fell between 1393.3 and 1534.4 MPa and the artificial neural network (ANN) demonstrated closely with simulated results. Shanmugam et al. 2010 used a three-dimensional finite element model to analyse the temperature distribution in a T-joint weld and studied the finite element method for predicting the bead geometry of laser-welded 1.6 mm thick sheets of AISI 304 austenitic stainless steel. They discovered that proper fusion of base material and tie between the beads profiles are achieved when the laser system is operated with a 60°-beam incident angle, a non-penetration defect is found at a beam angle of 30° beams, and at 45° beams, proper fusion of base materials is achieved and no tie exists between the resulting bead profiles. When the simulated and experimental findings are compared, the standard errors for the depth of penetration and bead width values are 1.9% and 2.78%, respectively. Different researchers have investigated on different grades of austenitic stainless steel (ASS) and found that there is a massive demand of simulation process in the industries such as nuclear processing plants, fast breeder reactors, pressurised water reactors and boiling water reactors before experimental process due to the cost-effectiveness of the material. Therefore, the objective

of this research focusses on the stress distribution in the weld zone by different welding speeds. The current study employs two welding processes—gas metal arc welding (GMAW) and shielded metal arc welding (SMAW)—in the ultra-low nickel austenitic stainless steel using two fillers (ER 308L and ER 308L-16) by varying welding speeds. The experimental yield stress is compared with Von Mises stress in the ANSYS software R16.0.

Methodology

Ultra-low nickel Cr-Mn austenitic stainless-steel plates with dimensions of $120 \times 75 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$ were prepared using band saw cutting. The base material contained 0.09% C, 0.29% Ni, 9.8% Mn, 14% Cr, and other alloying elements as specified in Table 1. Two filler materials were selected: ER308L-16 electrode (3.2 mm diameter) for SMAW and ER308L wire (1.2 mm diameter) for GMAW, both conforming to AWS specifications for austenitic stainless-steel welding.

Single V-butt joints were prepared for both welding

Table 1. Chemical composition of base metal, electrode and filler wire in wt %

Elements	C	Ni	Mn	Cr	P	S	Si	Mo	Cu	Al	N
Cr-Mn ASS	0.09	0.29	9.8	14	0.1	0.06	0.44	0.01	0.9	0.02	0.23
308L-16	0.03	9.5	1.3	19.9	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.1	-	-	-
E308L	0.03	10.4	0.8	19.4	0.04	0.01	0.116	0.81	-	-	-

processes. Three welding speeds were investigated as Low Welding Speed (LWS) at 3 mm/s, Medium Welding Speed (MWS) at 4.5 mm/s, and High Welding Speed (HWS) at 6 mm/s. For GMAW, welding currents ranged from 140–200 A with voltages of 17–21 V, while SMAW employed currents of 90–110 A with voltages of 21–24 V. Pure argon (99%) was used as shielding gas in GMAW at a flow rate of 14 L/min with wire feed rate of 100 lpm (Mvola and Kah 2017). Table 2 represents the welding parameters for SMAW and GMAW process.

Table 2. Welding Parameters for SMAW and GMAW process

Welding Method	Welding speed (mm/s)	Current(A)	Voltage(V)	Heat input (KJ/mm)
SMAW	3	90	21	0.441
	4.5	100	22	0.342
	6	110	24	0.308
GMAW	3	140	17	0.666
	4.5	170	19	0.602
	6	200	21	0.588

Heat Input is given by $Q = VI/v \text{ K J/mm}$

V = arc voltage in Volts (V)

I = welding Current in Amperes (A)

v = welding Speed (mm/s)

η = arc efficiency

$\eta = 0.7$ for Shielded Metal Arc Welding

$\eta = 0.84$ for Gas Metal Arc Welding

Tensile test specimens were prepared according to ASTM E-08 standard for yield stress determination (Tembhurkar et al. 2021). Universal tensile testing machine was employed with constant loading rate to measure yield strengths of welded samples at different welding speeds for both processes.

Finite element analysis

Comprehensive numerical simulation was conducted using ANSYS APDL (ANSYS Parametric Design Language). Three-dimensional models incorporating actual plate dimensions and weld bead geometry were developed. Mesh generation was optimized to ensure convergence and accuracy in the weld zone and heat-affected zone regions (Farias et al. 2021). The simulation methodology involved sequential coupled thermal-structural analysis. Mesh refinement in coupled thermal-structural analysis of Ultra-low nickel Cr-Mn austenitic stainless-steel plates should be guided by accuracy needs to capture steep temperature gradients and stress concentrations, particularly near boundaries, heat sources, and geometric discontinuities. Boundary conditions must reflect realistic thermal and mechanical loading for the plate dimensions ($120 \times 75 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$), including temperature distribution, heat flux profiles, fixed or simply supported edges, and any imposed displacements or pressures, to simulate service environments adequately.

Transient Thermal Analysis

Heat input was applied as a moving heat source along the weld centreline, considering temperature-dependent material properties including thermal conductivity, specific heat, and density. Convection and radiation boundary conditions were applied to all exposed surfaces.

Transient Structural Analysis

Temperature fields from thermal analysis were imported as thermal loads for stress calculation. Material properties including elastic modulus, Poisson's ratio, and thermal expansion coefficient were defined as functions of temperature. Von-Mises equivalent stress distributions were computed to evaluate residual stress patterns. The finite element model validation was performed by comparing simulation results with experimental yield stress measurements, ensuring the reliability of numerical predictions for both GMAW and SMAW processes across all welding speed conditions.

Comparative stress analysis of GMAW vs SMAW welding processes

The finite element analysis compares Von-Mises stress distributions across different welding speeds for Gas Metal Arc Welding (GMAW) and Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW) processes. GMAW results (Fig. 1a–c) shows low speed (Fig. 1a) has Maximum stress of 534 MPa with narrow, concentrated stress band, medium speed (Fig. 1b) has peak stress increases to 464 MPa with broader stress

distribution and high speed (Fig. 1c) shows Stress reduces to 409 MPa with more uniform heat-affected zone. SMAW results (Fig. 1d–f) show low speed (Fig. 1d) has maximum stress of 678 MPa showing diagonal stress pattern. Medium speed (Fig. 1e) has stress of 610 MPa with asymmetric distribution. High speed (Fig. 1f) has stress of 566 MPa with distinct angular stress concentration. The SMAW consistently produces higher peak stresses than GMAW across all welding speeds. Low welding speeds generate maximum stress concentrations in both processes. GMAW shows more symmetric stress patterns, while SMAW exhibits angular/diagonal distributions. High-speed SMAW produces the most critical stress state (566 MPa). The superior performance of GMAW at lower stress levels suggests better heat distribution and thermal management. SMAW's higher stress concentrations indicate more localized heating effects, potentially leading to greater residual stresses and distortion. The angular stress patterns in SMAW may result from electrode manipulation and discontinuous heat input. Medium welding speeds appear to create optimal conditions for stress concentration in both processes, likely due to the balance between heat input rate and dissipation time. For critical structural applications, GMAW at low-to-medium speeds offers better stress management, while SMAW requires careful speed optimization to minimize peak stresses and associated distortion risks.

Results and discussion

Yield Stress Analysis

The experimental yield stress measurements revealed distinct patterns for both welding processes. In GMAW, yield stresses of 628, 460, and 454 MPa were obtained for low, medium, and high welding speeds respectively, while SMAW exhibited yield stresses of 502, 480, and 440 MPa under similar conditions (Ambade et al. 2024). The consistent decrease in yield strength with increasing welding speed can be attributed to reduced heat input per unit length, resulting in faster cooling rates and refined microstructural features in the heat-affected zone.

Von-Mises Stress Distribution Analysis

The finite element analysis using ANSYS APDL provided comprehensive stress distribution data for both welding processes. Fig. 1 demonstrates the evolution of stress patterns across different welding speeds, revealing critical insights into the thermal-mechanical behaviour of ultra-low nickel Cr-Mn austenitic stainless-steel welds.

The simulation results for GMAW showed Von-Mises stresses of 534 MPa, 464 MPa, and 409 MPa for low, medium, and high welding speeds respectively. These values correlate well with experimental yield stress measurements, with the finite element results being approximately 15% lower than experimental values as shown in Table 3.

Figure 1. Von-Mises Stress of GMAW (a) Low (b) Medium (c) High Welding Speed and SMAW at (d) Low (e) Medium (f) High Welding Speed.

This discrepancy can be attributed to the idealized boundary conditions in the simulation model and the assumption of perfect heat transfer coefficients. SMAW demonstrated significantly higher stress concentrations with Von-Mises stresses of 678 MPa, 610 MPa, and 566 MPa for low, medium, and high welding speeds respectively. It is important to point out that the simulation results

surpassed the experimental yield stresses by about 35% as shown in Table 3. This suggests that localized stress concentrations exist which exceed the yield strength of the material, and could thus cause plastic deformation in crucial areas of the weld. Yield strength changes resulting from solid-state phase transformations have a significant impact on stress concentration during welding.

Table 3. Comparison of Experimental and Von-Misses stress values

Welding Method	Welding Speed	Yield Stress (MPa) (experimental)	Von Mises Stress (MPa)
GMAW	LWS	628	534
	MWS	460	464
	HWS	454	409
SMAW	LWS	502	678
	MWS	480	610
	HWS	440	566

Comparative analysis and process optimization

The comparative analysis reveals that SMAW consistently produces higher residual stresses than GMAW across all welding speeds. This phenomenon is primarily attributed to the broader weld bead profile in SMAW (Figs 2, 3), which results in greater heat input and more extensive thermal cycling of the base material. The wider heat-affected zone in SMAW creates larger thermal gradients and consequently higher residual stresses.

The mesh convergence studies (Figs 4, 5) validated the numerical model accuracy, while the transient thermal analysis (Fig 1a–c) confirmed the expected temperature gradient from the weld centreline to the base material. The stress concentration patterns in Fig. 1d–f clearly demonstrate the butterfly-wing distribution characteristic of butt-joint welding, with peak stresses occurring at the weld toe regions.

Welding speed optimization

The inverse relationship between welding speed and residual stress is consistent across both processes. Higher welding speeds (6 mm/s) resulted in 23% and 17% stress reduction in GMAW and SMAW respectively, compared to low welding speeds (3 mm/s). This reduction is attributed to decreased heat input per unit length, minimizing thermal distortion and associated residual stresses.

Figure 2. Transverse view of Model in ANSYS APDL of GMAW.

Figure 3. Transverse view of Model in ANSYS APDL of SMAW.

Figure 4. Meshing of Models of GMAW.

Figure 5. Meshing of Models of SMAW.

Process selection criteria

From a stress management perspective, GMAW demonstrates superior performance with lower residual stresses and better correlation between experimental and numerical results. The narrower weld bead geometry in GMAW provides more controlled heat input, making it preferable for applications requiring minimal post-weld stress relief treatments. However, SMAW's higher stress levels may be acceptable in applications where joint strength requirements outweigh residual stress concerns due to the wider HAZ in SMAW process (Alipooramirabad et al. 2017). The finite element validation confirms that both processes can be optimized through welding speed control, with high-speed welding offering the best compromise between productivity and stress minimization in ultra-low nickel Cr-Mn austenitic stainless-steel applications.

Conclusions

Based on the comprehensive finite element analysis and experimental investigation of ultra-low nickel Cr-Mn

ASS welded using GMAW and SMAW techniques, the following conclusions have been drawn:

1. The finite element analysis conducted in ANSYS successfully validated the inverse relationship between welding speed and residual stress.
2. According to simulation results, GMAW shows lower simulation yield stresses than experimental by 15%.
3. SMAW exhibited higher residual stress concentrations with experimental yield stresses by 35% suggesting potential plastic deformation in critical weld regions.
4. It was observed that at high welding speed, there is reduction in residual stress of 23% in GMAW and 17% in SMAW compared to low welding speed.
5. GMAW proved superior to SMAW in terms of residual stress, producing consistently lower stress concentrations due to its narrower weld bead geometry and more controlled heat input. The wider heat-affected zone in SMAW resulted in greater thermal gradients and consequently higher residual stresses, making GMAW the preferred choice for stress-critical applications.

References

- Akbari D, Sattari-far I (2017) Effect of edge preparation on residual stress of welding in dissimilar joints. *Modares Mechanical Engineering* 17(7): 307–315.
- Alipooramirabad H, Paradowska A, Ghomashchi R, Reid M (2017) Investigating the effects of welding process on residual stresses, microstructure and mechanical properties in HSLA steel welds. *Journal of Manufacturing Processes* 28: 70–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2017.04.030>
- Almeida DF, Martins RF, Cardoso JB (2017) Numerical simulation of residual stresses induced by TIG butt-welding of thin plates made of AISI 316L stainless steel. *Procedia Structural Integrity* 5: 633–639. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2017.07.032>
- Ambade SP, Tembhurkar CK, Patil A, Tidke AV, Shelare SD, Prakash C, Djukic MB, Khosravi N, Paramasivam P (2024) Microstructure, mechanical properties and sensitization of ultra-low nickel Cr-Mn austenitic stainless steels. *Journal of Materials Research and Technology* 30: 4353–4365. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2024.04.127>
- Arora H, Singh R, Brar GS (2019) Thermal and structural modelling of arc welding processes: A literature review. *Measurement and Control* 52(7–8): 955–969. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020294019857747>
- Efa DA (2024) Enhancing the efficiency of laser beam welding: multi-objective parametric optimization of dissimilar materials using finite element analysis. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology* 133(9): 4525–4541. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-024-13985-y>
- Farias RM, Teixeira PRF, Vilarinho LO (2021) An efficient computational approach for heat source optimization in numerical simulations of arc welding processes. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 176: 106382. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2020.106382>

- González-Velázquez JL (2018) Fractography and failure analysis. Vol. 24. Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 165 pp. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-76651-5>
- Gkatzogiannis S, Knoedel P, Ummenhofer T (2017) Influence of welding parameters on the welding residual stresses. VII International Conference on Computational Methods for Coupled Problems in Science and Engineering, 767–778.
- Mvola B, Kah P (2017) Effects of shielding gas control: welded joint properties in GMAW process optimization. The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology 88(9): 2369–2387. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-016-8936-2>
- Naseem A, Ilyas M, Shehbaz T, Hussain G, Alkahtani M (2024) Microstructural and mechanical characterization of electron beam welded low-nickel nitrogen-strengthened austenitic stainless steel. Heliyon 10(14): e34315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e34315>
- Rizvi SA, Ahamad M (2018) Effect of heat input on the microstructure and mechanical properties of a Welded joint-A Review. International Journal of Applied Engineering Research 13(6): 184–188.
- Singh A, Singh RP (2020) A review of effect of welding parameters on the mechanical properties of weld in submerged arc welding process. Materials Today: Proceedings 26: 1714–1717. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.02.361>
- Shanmugam NS, Buvanashakaran G, Sankaranarayanan K, Kumar SR (2010). A transient finite element simulation of the temperature and bead profiles of T-joint laser welds. Materials and Design 31(9): 4528–4542. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2010.03.057>
- Sepe R, Giannella V, Greco A, De Luca A (2021) FEM simulation and experimental tests on the SMAW welding of a dissimilar t-joint. Metals 11(7): 1016. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met11071016>
- Tembhurkar C, Kataria R, Ambade S, Verma J, Sharma A, Sarkar S (2021) Effect of fillers and autogenous welding on dissimilar welded 316L austenitic and 430 ferritic stainless steels. Journal of Materials Engineering and Performance 30(2): 1444–1453. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11665-020-05395-4>